

Use of social networking tools and services among research scholars at the University of Kerala

L. R. Divya* and K. G. Sudhier**

To Cite: Divya, L.R. & Sudhier, K.G. (2019). Use of social networking tools and services among research scholars at the University of Kerala. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 9(1), 23-28.

*Lecturer (Contract)
School of Distance Education
University of Kerala
Senate House Campus,
Thiruvananthapuram-Kerala

**Assistant Professor
DLIS
Central University of Tamil
Nadu,
Neelakudi Campus,
Kangalancherry
Thiruvavarur-Tamil Nadu

Corresponding Author
K.G. Sudhier
kgsudhier@cutn.ac.in

TIME LAG

Received on : 26.05.18
Revised on : 08.01.19
Accepted on : 18.02.19

Online Access

www.ijdt.com

DOI
10.5958/2249-5576.2019.00005.0

QR Barcode

ABSTRACT

The study investigates the scholarly use of social networking tools and services by the doctoral students at the University of Kerala. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data from a population of 649 full-time doctoral students from different departments of the university. The analysis revealed that most of the researchers were daily users of the internet for 'research purposes' and 'email' is the most preferred social networking services preferred by them. Statistical analysis shows that the majority of the social networking tools and services have no significant difference with the gender of researchers except in the use of blogging service. It was also revealed that there is a significant difference in the use of social networking tools and services by the researchers with respect to their faculty. The major obstacles faced by research scholars are 'overload of information' the study provides useful insight to promote the use of social networking tools and services among the research scholars in the University of Kerala.

KeyTerms: Internet, Social Networking Sites, Research Scholars, Social Networking Tools and Services, Research scholars, University of Kerala

INTRODUCTION

Social networking sites are the virtual space among the mass who mutually share their ideas information and use it as an effective means of communication with each other. It is possible in all types of academic institutions or any other sites of common interest. The SNSs refers to a wide range of rapidly developing services, tools and practices. It can be broadly defined as internet or mobile device- based social spaces designed to facilitate communication, collaboration and content sharing across networks of contacts Singh & Gill¹. Facebook, Twitter, Myspace, LinkedIn etc. are the available most popular SNSs.

A social networking service is a platform to build social networks or social relations among people who share similar personal and career interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. Most social network services are web-based and provide means for users to interact over the internet such as e-mail and instant messaging. Social networking sites allow users to share ideas, pictures, posts, activities, events and interests with people in their network².

Boyd & Ellison defined social networking services as web based services that allow

individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system; articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection and view their list of connections and those made by others within the system³.

The University of Travancore which eventually became the University of Kerala was established in 1937 by a promulgation of the Maharaja of Travancore, Sri Chithira Thirunal Balarama Varma who was also the first Chancellor of the university. The university consists of 42 departments, including the school of distance education are now categorized under 11 recognized schools. All these departments conduct postgraduate, M.Phil., Ph.D. and teaching activities. The research activities in the institution of the department of research are started under university in the same year of establishment. The research programs in various disciplines are undertaken by centres of teaching and research departments recognized by the University⁴.

The study has been conducted to explore the use of SNSs tools and services by the research scholars of the University of Kerala. It has also covered various hindrances which are encountered by the users while accessing these sites.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A large number of studies had been conducted by researchers throughout the world regarding 'Social Networking Sites' for the last several years. Munshi, Mostafa & Alam studied the use of social networking sites for educational purposes among the postgraduate students at the University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh⁵. The study shows that the students have a positive attitude towards the role of social networking sites for their academic purposes. Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that SNSs help their educational field and it builds up a good relationship between their friends, family, educators, etc. Jeysankar, Nachiappan & Suresh investigated the access to and use of social networking sites among the postgraduate students of rural colleges in India⁶. The respondents have excellent skills in using social networking sites for sharing and communicating information. Ashraf & Haneefa investigated the scholarly use of social media by the doctoral students in the University of Calicut, Kerala⁷. The analysis revealed that the majority of the students are aware and use social media for scholarly purpose and mainly for locating scholarly content and current awareness. Wikis and social networking sites are the most widely used social media by the students.

Singh & Gill in their study on the role and users' approach to social networking sites in the universities of North India revealed that Facebook is the most popular SNS by all categories of respondents⁸. Majority of respondents were aware of the security aspects of SNSs and it signified that excessive time consumption and fear of misusing personal information were the major hurdles in the way of accessing SNSs. Munshi studied the use of social media and internet communication tools in academic purposes of the engineering students at Aligarh Muslim University and discovered that the majority of the students are 'highly independent on Internet communication tools and social media for their academic and communication purposes in social life⁹'. However, students faced few problems while they are accessing these tools e.g. poor connectivity, lack of infrastructure, lack of time, etc. Divya & Sudhier studied the use of internet tools and services by research scholars of the faculty of applied sciences in the University of Kerala¹⁰. The study revealed that the majority of the research scholars use internet for e-journal access and research purpose. Results indicated that e-mail is the most commonly used web service among research scholars. The usage pattern of Facebook by the students of information science and library management department at Dhaka University was studied by Islam & Mostofa¹¹. The study also revealed that personality characteristics, gender, educational level, geographical area and age influence ISLM students' patterns of Facebook use and their perceptions about Facebook. Sahoo & Sharma¹² described social networking in library affairs. From the traditional searching process for the books in the libraries, the interactive usage of social networking can be now addressed as part of the library system.

Kumar & Kumar made an attempt to study the activities and reasons for using SNS by the postgraduate students and research scholars of Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak¹³. It was found that majority of the respondents to be aware and making use of such applications in their research work. The study also revealed that Facebook is the most popular SNSs among all categories of students and research scholars. Chu & Du investigated the use of social networking tools in academic libraries like Asia, North America and Europe by examining the extent of their use, library staff's perceptions of their usefulness and challenges, and factors influencing decisions to use or not to use such tools¹⁴.

Facebook and Twitter were the most commonly adopted tools in university libraries. The study offered insights for academic librarians to make informed decisions in applying social networking tools. Hamat, Embi & Hassan found that a large number of Malaysian university students spend their time using social networking sites¹⁵. The interesting finding comes out from the study that the majority of the students believed to be spending maximum time on SNSs are not affecting their academic performances.

Chen, Chu & Xu in their study found that among the four types of interactions, knowledge sharing attracts the largest volume of user responses on libraries' SNSs¹⁶. In order to improve the efficiency of interacting with users on SNSs, there are necessities for libraries to coordinate different types of SNSs and take the properties of their communities under consideration. Jahan & Ahmed reported the results of perceptions of academic use of social networking sites by students of the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh¹⁷. The results of the questionnaire survey indicated a positive attitude towards the academic use of SNSs by the students. The higher academic institutions need to devise appropriate policies and strategies on how they can utilize social networking sites to support education and learning beyond the classroom. Haneefa & Sumita investigated the perception and use of SNS by the students of Calicut University, Kerala¹⁸. The study revealed that students are aware of SNS and used it mainly for friendly communication. Lack of security and privacy in SNS was observed as the main problems. Singh & Gill conducted a study through a structured questionnaire administrated among the research scholars pursuing their research at GND University, Amritsar¹⁹. The study found that majority of the respondents were aware of SNSs and making use of such applications in their research affairs.

The aim of the study conducted by Bicen & Cavus was to investigate the internet usage of students and also to learn which social network sites are preferred by the participants²⁰. The questionnaire was used to collect data and to find out the opinions of students about preferring social network sites. The results of the study showed that Live Spaces and Facebook were preferred by the participants. Park studied the differences in the perception and use among university students and faculties in social networking site²¹. The implications for academic library services were clearly identified. The present study has been conducted to explore the use of SNSs tools and services by the research scholars of the University of Kerala. It has also covered various hindrances which are encountered by the users while accessing these sites.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the place and purpose of internet access
- To identify most frequently used social networking tools and services
- To assess the gender and faculty wise use of SNT&S
- To identify the problems faced by the research scholars in using SN tools and services

METHODOLOGY

The population of the study includes the 825 full-time doctoral students of the University of Kerala. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data from a population of 825 full-time doctoral students from different departments of the university. Out of the 736 questionnaires distributed, 649 questionnaires were returned (response rate 88.1%). The collected data was further transferred to a computerized database and for analysis MS Excel and SPSS version 17.0 are

used for specific, descriptive and inferential statistics. Appropriate tests like Mann-Whitney Test (U-Test) and Kruskal-Wallis Test (H-Test) are used to establish statistical significance.

DATA ANALYSIS

Demographic Information

Table 1 represents the combined data on population size, gender and age groups of the respondents. It is evident that the majority of the research scholars are in the age group of 25-30 (53.2%). As far as the gender of the research scholars is concerned the majority of them are females 65.3% and the rest 34.7% are male researchers. Faculty-wise distribution of researchers shows that 228 (35.1%) of them are from the faculty of arts and 170 researchers (26.2%) are from science. 349 (53.8%) research scholars possess PG degree as basic qualification and 300 (46.2%) possess M.Phil. degree as a higher qualification. In the case of research centers, 363 (55.9%) respondents are from various research departments and 286 (44.1%) are from the Kerala university library.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Demographic Information		Responses	% age
Age	< 25	99	15.3
	25 - 30	345	53.2
	30<	205	31.6
Gender	Male	225	34.7
	Female	424	65.3
Faculty	Science	170	26.2
	Social Science	121	18.6
	Arts	228	35.1
	Commerce	72	11.1
	Others	58	8.9
Educational Qualification	P G	349	53.8
	M.Phil.	300	46.2
Research Center	Departments	363	55.9
	Kerala university Library	286	44.1

Place of Internet Access

Fig. 1 examines the research scholar's place of internet access. From the analysis, it is clear that research centers in Kerala University are highly efficient in providing internet services to the research scholars. The average score is taken for each place of internet access. The priority of the place of internet access shows that 498 (76.7%) respondents access the internet from 'department or university library' ranked first followed by 470 (72.4%) from 'home or hostel'. Thus the result of the study indicates that internet facility still needs to be strengthened at the campus library. Distribution of the place of internet access is shown in fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Distribution of the Place of Internet Access

Purpose of Internet Use

Table 2 showed the research scholar's purpose of internet use. The research scholar's use of the internet is an important area of study in the wired information environment. The internet has become an important component in academic institutions. Ranking of internet usage is based on the mean of the preference of choices are given in table 2. It indicates that most of the research scholars in the University of Kerala are daily users of the internet for 'research purposes' 418 (64.4%) and 338 (52.1%) respondents daily use internet for 'quick access of information', followed by 'e-mail checking' 380 (58.6%). Most of the scholars 198 (30.5%) monthly use internet for 'e-book' access.

The analysis revealed that majority of the respondents i.e. mean value 3.5 use internet for their 'research purpose', while for 'checking email' and 'quick access of information' is the other purposes specified by research scholars.

Table 2: Purpose of Internet Use

Purpose of Internet Use	Daily	Twice a week	Once a week	Monthly
Checking email	380 (58.6%)	126 (19.4%)	90 (13.9%)	53 (8.2%)
Research purpose	418 (64.4%)	136 (21%)	77 (11.9%)	18 (2.8%)
Quick access of information	338 (52.1%)	191 (29.4%)	111 (17.1%)	9 (1.4%)
Social networking	274 (42.2%)	146 (22.5%)	130 (20%)	99 (15.3%)
E-Books	106 (16.3%)	175 (27%)	170 (26.2%)	198 (30.5%)
E- Journals	172 (26.6%)	183 (28.3%)	153 (23.6%)	139 (21.5%)
Online Databases	93 (14.4%)	174 (26.9%)	201 (31%)	180 (27.8%)
Recreation	94 (14.5%)	190 (29.3%)	216 (33.3%)	149 (23%)
Career development	127 (19.6%)	214 (33%)	192 (29.6%)	116 (17.9%)

Preference of the Use of Social Networking Tools and Services

It is inferred from the table 3 that the majority of the respondents prefer 'e-mail' as the most used social networking service with a mean value 22.4, which is ranked highest in the mean scoring rating. Usage of 'world wide web' ranked second with mean value 20.6. Services like 'search engines' ranked third with mean value 17.6.

Table 3: Preference of the Use of Social Networking Tools and Services

Social Networking Tools and Services	Mean	SD	Rank
Email	22.4	2.0	1
World Wide Web	20.6	5.0	2
Frequently Asked Questions	11.0	6.6	14
File Transfer Protocol(FTP)	8.5	6.5	19
Telnet	5.7	5.2	24
Bulletin Board Services	6.7	5.2	23
Blogging (E.g. Weblogs, Blogger/ Word press)	9.8	5.7	18
Audio/Video sharing/Webcasting (E.g. Flickr, Skype, YouTube)	13.0	6.2	10
Audio and Video Conferencing	10.1	5.5	17
Instant Messaging	10.9	5.7	15
Chat	12.6	6.2	11
Search Engines	17.6	4.9	3
Discussion Forums (Google/Yahoo! Groups)	13.3	5.3	8
RSS feeds	10.4	5.1	16
Google Scholar, Google Scholar Alert	16.9	5.3	5
Databases E.g. Scopus	12.5	5.9	12
GoogleDocs, Google Apps	13.3	5.5	9
Research Gate, Academia.edu, getCITED.org, Social Science Research Network (SSRN.com)	17.0	5.1	4
Wikis (Wikipedia)	16.3	6.0	6
Social bookmarking/aggregating (E.g. Delicious, Tags, Folksonomy)	11.6	5.4	13
Social Networking (E.g. Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Google +)	15.7	5.8	7
Content Management Systems (E.g. Drupal, Joomla)	8.3	5.0	21
Reference Management System (E.g. Zotero, Mendeley, Citeulike)	7.6	5.4	22
Slide Share, Fig Share	8.3	5.2	20

engines' and networks like 'research gates', 'academia.edu' etc. ranked 3rd and 4th with mean value 17.6 and 17.0 respectively.

○ Use of Social Networking Tools and Services-Gender wise

Table 4 identified that 'email' is the most preferred social networking services preferred by the research scholars in the University of Kerala followed by 'world wide web'. The average score regarding the male researchers use of 'search engine' (mean value= 17.8) is slightly greater than that of female (mean value= 17.6). 'Research Gate', 'Academia.edu', 'getCITED.org', 'Social Science Research Network' usage is more among the females than male respondents. From the results, it can also be observed that the use of 'Wikipedia' is more among females than males. 'Telnet', 'Bulletin Board Services' are the least preferred internet services. Priority shows that there is no exact agreement between social networking tools and services with respect to gender.

Mann-Whitney test revealed that the gender of Ph.D. scholars of University of Kerala shows a significant difference in the use of blogging services (Z=2.73**, P=0.006). Majority of the other social networking tools and services have no significant difference with gender.

Table 4: Use of Social Networking Tools and Services-Gender Wise

Social Networking Tools and Services	Male		Female		Z#	p
	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank		
Email	22.4 ± 1.9	1	22.3 ± 2	1	0.36	0.722
World Wide Web	20.7 ± 4.9	2	20.6 ± 5.1	2	0.38	0.707
Frequently Asked Questions	11.3 ± 6.6	13	10.9 ± 6.6	15	0.99	0.325
File Transfer Protocol	9 ± 6.9	19	8.2 ± 6.3	21	1.17	0.244
Telnet	6.3 ± 5.5	24	5.4 ± 5	24	2.39*	0.017
Bulletin Board Services	7 ± 5.5	23	6.6 ± 5.1	23	0.77	0.440
Blogging	10.5 ± 5.8	16	9.4 ± 5.6	18	2.73**	0.006
Audio/Video sharing/Webcasting	13.2 ± 6.2	8	12.8 ± 6.2	10	0.72	0.473
Audio and Video Conferencing	10.5 ± 5.3	17	9.8 ± 5.6	17	1.59	0.112
Instant Messaging	10.7 ± 5.6	15	11.1 ± 5.7	14	0.59	0.559
Chat	13.1 ± 6.3	10	12.3 ± 6.2	12	1.58	0.115
Search Engines	17.8 ± 4.7	3	17.6 ± 5	3	0.32	0.751
Discussion Forums	13.2 ± 5	9	13.4 ± 5.4	8	0.44	0.662
RSS feeds	10.2 ± 5.3	18	10.5 ± 5	16	0.75	0.451
GoogleScholar, Google Scholar Alert	16.6 ± 5.2	4	17 ± 5.4	5	1.15	0.252
Databases Eg.Scopus	12.2 ± 5.8	12	12.7 ± 6	11	0.94	0.349
GoogleDocs, Google Apps	13.1 ± 5.6	11	13.4 ± 5.4	9	0.57	0.570
Research Gate, Academia.edu, getCITED.org, Social Science Research Network	16.4 ± 5.4	5	17.3 ± 5	4	2.15*	0.032
Wikis	15.7 ± 6.5	7	16.6 ± 5.7	6	1	0.319
Social book marking/aggregating	11.1 ± 5.6	14	11.9 ± 5.3	13	1.48	0.138
Social Networking Sites	16 ± 5.5	6	15.6 ± 6	7	0.52	0.603
Content Management Systems	7.9 ± 4.8	20	8.6 ± 5.1	20	1.56	0.118
Reference Management System	7.6 ± 5.7	22	7.7 ± 5.2	22	0.5	0.618
Slide Share, FigShare	7.7 ± 5.2	21	8.6 ± 5.3	19	2.04*	0.041

#Mann-Whitney U Test**:- Significant at 0.01 level, *:- Significant at 0.05 level

○ Use of social networking Tools and Services-Faculty Wise

Faculty-wise analysis of the use of social networking tools and services is shown in table 5. 'Email' is the most preferred social networking services among the research scholars in the University of Kerala followed by 'World Wide Web'. While applying the Kruskal Wallis Test, it is found that the average score of search engines are more among social science and arts faculties (mean value=18.1) than the other faculties. Social networking services like 'Research Gate', 'Academia.edu', 'getCITED.org', 'Social Science Research Network' are higher in commerce faculty (mean value=18.2). Ranking of the use of social networking tools and services by the research scholars shows that there is no exact agreement between the faculties.

The statistical test revealed that there is a significant difference in the use of social networking tools and services by the researchers with respect to their faculty.

Table 5: Use of Social Networking Tools and Services-Faculty Wise

Social Networking tools and services	Science		Social Science		Arts		Commerce		Others		2#	P
	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank		
Email	22.5 ± 1.9	1	22.1 ± 2	1	22.2 ± 2	1	23.2 ± 1.3	1	21.9 ± 2.4	1	28.31**	0
World Wide Web	18.9 ± 6.8	2	22.1 ± 3.1	2	20.6 ± 4.6	2	21.7 ± 3.6	2	21.6 ± 3	2	19.26**	0.001
Frequently Asked Questions	9.3 ± 6.8	20	13.3 ± 5.8	9	10.7 ± 6.6	14	12.1 ± 6.3	11	11.1 ± 7	14	26.34**	0
File Transfer Protocol	7.4 ± 6.6	22	8.2 ± 6	20	8.9 ± 6.8	19	10.2 ± 6	15	8.5 ± 6.4	19	13.38**	0.01
Telnet	5.3 ± 5.7	24	6.4 ± 5.9	24	5 ± 3.9	24	8.2 ± 6.2	21	5.3 ± 3.6	24	24.74**	0
Bulletin Board Services	6.6 ± 5.2	23	7.4 ± 5	23	5.7 ± 4.7	23	7.7 ± 6.1	22	8.5 ± 5.9	20	20.56**	0
Blogging	10 ± 4.7	16	9.1 ± 5.6	18	10 ± 6.3	16	9.2 ± 6	19	10.5 ± 5.5	16	4.12	0.39
Audio/Video sharing/Webcasting	12.5 ± 5.8	10	13.5 ± 6.6	8	12.7 ± 6.3	12	11.9 ± 5.1	12	15.9 ± 5.7	8	18.82**	0.00
Audio and Video Conferencing	9.7 ± 5.7	19	11.2 ± 5.7	14	9.8 ± 5.2	18	9.1 ± 6	20	10.9 ± 4.7	15	10.99*	0.027
Instant Messaging	10.9 ± 5.6	15	12.2 ± 5.1	13	10.7 ± 6.1	15	9.3 ± 5.4	18	11.4 ± 5.1	13	13.56**	0.009

Social Networking tools and services	Science		Social Science		Arts		Commerce		Others		2#	P
	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank	Mean ± SD	Rank		
Chat	12.5 ± 5.2	9	10.7 ± 7.4	16	13.3 ± 6.4	9	13.6 ± 5.5	9	12.8 ± 6.1	11	14.93**	0.005
Search Engines	17.1 ± 4.9	5	18.2 ± 5.3	3	18 ± 4.5	3	18.1 ± 4.9	4	16.5 ± 5.5	5	8.93	0.063
Discussion Forums	12.3 ± 4.8	11	13.2 ± 5.8	10	13.2 ± 5.3	10	13.9 ± 5	8	16.5 ± 4.4	6	30.55**	0
RSS feeds	11.5 ± 4.5	14	10.8 ± 5.2	15	9.8 ± 5.2	17	9.4 ± 5.5	17	9.7 ± 5.1	17	17.68**	0.001
Google Scholar, Google Scholar Alert	18.5 ± 5.3	3	17.6 ± 4.5	4	16.2 ± 5.1	7	14.5 ± 5.9	7	15.9 ± 5.9	7	38.03**	0
Databases Eg. Scopus	12 ± 6.2	13	12.5 ± 5.6	12	13.1 ± 5.8	11	11.8 ± 6.9	13	12.3 ± 4.8	12	4.8	0.309
GoogleDocs, Google Apps	13.1 ± 5.9	8	12.7 ± 5.7	11	14 ± 5.1	8	11 ± 4.5	14	14.9 ± 5.2	10	23.85**	0
Research Gate, Academia.edu, getCITED.org, Social Science Research Network	18 ± 5	4	15.5 ± 6.1	6	16.7 ± 4.7	4	18.2 ± 5	3	16.6 ± 4.3	4	24.1**	0
Wikis	16 ± 6.1	6	15.9 ± 6	5	16.6 ± 6.1	5	16 ± 5.9	5	16.9 ± 4.9	3	3.12	0.537
Social bookmarking/ aggregating	12.1 ± 5.9	12	10 ± 5.3	17	12.4 ± 4.9	13	13 ± 4.8	10	9 ± 5.2	18	35.82**	0
Social Networking Sites	15.8 ± 5.8	7	14.3 ± 5.4	7	16.4 ± 6	6	15.4 ± 5.7	6	15.6 ± 5.8	9	14.35**	0.006
Content Management Systems	9.9 ± 5.7	18	7.5 ± 3.9	21	8.5 ± 4.9	21	7 ± 3.8	23	6.3 ± 5.2	21	31.03**	0
Reference Management System	10 ± 5.6	17	7.4 ± 5.4	22	7 ± 4.8	22	5.9 ± 4.6	24	5.9 ± 5.7	22	48.58**	0
Slide Share, Fig Share	8.2 ± 4.8	21	8.5 ± 5.9	19	8.6 ± 4.9	20	9.5 ± 6.1	16	5.7 ± 4.4	23	19.23**	0.001

#Kruskal Wallis Test**: - Significant at 0.01 level, *: - Significant at 0.05 level

○ Problems in Using Social Networking Tools and Services

Researchers are facing many problems while using social networking tools and services. The scholars were asked to indicate their problems encountered while using SNSs. The study revealed that major obstacles faced by research scholars are 'overload of information' and 'distraction from the initial purpose for accessing the internet' (mean value = 4.1). 'Theft of personal information' through social networking services is the least preferred problem faced by the respondents. Problems in using social networking tools and services are shown in fig 2.

Table 6: Problems in Using Social Networking Tools and Services

Problems	Mean	SD	Rank
Overload of information	4.1	1.5	1
Distraction from the initial purpose for accessing the internet	4.1	1.5	2
Undesired content	3.9	1.6	3
Lack of authenticity of the information	3.9	1.7	4
Lack of a date stamp / Chronology issues	2.6	1.5	5
Theft of Personal Information	2.3	1.5	6

CONCLUSION

The study investigates the use of social networking tools and services use of research scholars in University of Kerala. It is found that 76.7% of respondent's access the internet from 'department or university library' ranked first followed from 'home or hostel'. Thus the result of the study indicates that internet facility still needs to be strengthened at the campus library. Most of the research scholars in the University of Kerala are daily users of the internet for their 'research purposes'. Email is the most preferred social networking services preferred by the research scholars. Mann-Whitney test proved that most of the social networking tools and services have no significant difference with gender. Kruskal Wallis test proved that there is a significant difference in the use of social networking tools and services by the researchers with respect to their faculty.

The internet is essential for research scholars as it brought all information scattered all over the world with the easy search. It helps researchers in accessing information without time lag.

Research scholars also use web based services for their research work. The research scholar's use of SNSs is an important area of study in today's wired information environment and it has become an essential component in academic activities. Hence the findings of this study will serve as an inspiration for the stakeholders of information managers and researchers and hope it will improve their knowledge and utilisation of social networking tools for academic purposes.

REFERENCES

- Singh, K. P. & Gill, M. S. (2015). Role and users' approach to social networking sites (SNSs): A study of universities of North India. *The Electronic Library*, 33(1), 9-34.
- Social Networking Services. Available at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_networking_service. (Accessed on 10.03.2018).
- Boyd, D. M. & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 28-32.
- The University of Kerala. Available at <http://www.keralauniversity.ac.in> (Accessed on 22.03.2018).
- Munshi, S. A., Mostafa, M. G. & Alam, M. M. (2018). Uses of social networking sites among postgraduate students at University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh: A study. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 38(1), 34-40.
- Jeysankar, R., Nachiappan, N & Suresh, M. (2016). Access and use of social networking sites (SNSs) among the post graduate students of rural based college of Tamil Nadu, India-A study. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 53(3), 237-241.
- Ashraf, K. & Haneefa, K. M. (2016). Scholarly use of social media. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 63(2), 132-139.
- Singh, K. P. & Gill, M. S. (2015). Role and users' approach to social networking sites (SNSs): A study of universities of North India. *The Electronic Library*, 33(1), 9-34.
- Munshi, S. A. (2015). The use of social media and internet

- communication tools in academic purposes of the engineering students at Aligarh Muslim University (AMU). *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 52(6), 479-487.
10. Divya, L. R. & Sudhier, K. G., Pillai. (2015). Use of internet tools and services by research scholars of the University of Kerala. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 52(6), 471-478.
 11. Islam, M. & Mostofa, M. (2015). The usage pattern of Facebook among the students of Dhaka University: A study. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 62(2), 133-137.
 12. Sahoo, D. R. & Sharma, D. ((2015). Social networking tools for library services. *International Journal of Innovations in Science, Engineering & Technology*, 2(3), 69-71.
 13. Kumar, A. & Kumar, R (2013). Use of social networking sites (SNSs): A study of Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1000. Available at <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1000> (Accessed on 10.03.2018)
 14. Chu, S. K.W. & Du, H (2013). Social networking tools for academic libraries. *Journal of Library & Information Science*, 45(1), 64-75.
 15. Hamat, A., Embi, M.A. & Hassan, H.A. (2012). The use of social networking sites among Malaysian university students. *International Education Studies*, 5(3), 56-66.
 16. Chen, D.Y.T., Chu, S.K.W. & Xu, S.Q. (2012). How do libraries use social networking sites to interact with users? *Proceedings of the ASIST*, 49(1), 1-10.
 17. Jahan, I. & Ahmed, S.Z. (2012). Students' perceptions of academic use of social networking sites: A survey of university students in Bangladesh. *Information Development*, 28(3), 235-247.
 18. Haneefa, K.M. & Sumita, E. (2011). Perception and use of social networking sites by the students of Calicut University. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 31(4), 295-301.
 19. Singh, K. P. & Gill, M. S. (2011). Use of social networking sites by the research scholars: A study of Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar. *Library Herald*, 49(3), 229-241.
 20. Bicen, H. & Cavus, N. (2010). The most preferred social network sites by students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 2(2), 5864-5869.
 21. Park, J. H. (2010). Differences among university students and faculties in social networking site perception and use: Implications for academic library services. *The Electronic Library*. 28(3), 417-31.